

DIFFERENTIATED INSTRUCTION AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION TO LANGUAGE TEACHING ISSUES OF 21st CENTURY

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Abstract. *The article discusses the actual problems related to language teaching and second language acquisition (SLA) processes of the 21st–globalized century. It also offers some effective teaching approaches of differentiated instruction as an alternative solution to the below-mentioned issues.*

Keywords: *SLA, language teaching, issues, technology integration, cultural competence, assessment.*

Introduction

In the twenty-first century, teaching languages presents a multitude of problems and obstacles that educators need to deal with, since it is the requirement of the current age to educate adequately the students for a worldwide society. Language teachers are always in need to modify their strategies to better suit the changing demands of their learners as a result of societal changes and technological breakthroughs.

Language teaching issues of recent years.

There are some scholars considering the most important issues of the century. For instance, according to Richards and Rodgers (2001), one of the most important concerns in language instruction in the twenty-first century is the necessity of using technology in the classroom to improve language acquisition. But at the same time, it serves as one of the biggest challenges that language teachers are facing. Even though technology can improve language learning by giving students to have interactive activities, to access to real materials, as well as communication tools, many educators find it difficult to integrate these resources into their teaching methods. Furthermore, differences in learning outcomes may result from the digital gap that separates students who have access to technology from those who do not.

According to Nunan (2003), fostering learner autonomy and critical thinking abilities is also from the concerns of language teaching needs of the globalized world today. Larsen-Freeman's (2000) consideration about adopting a more communicative and task-based approach to teaching, which reflects the changing needs and expectations of learners is another example of main concerns.

Since it is crucial for language learners to comprehend and value the cultural quirks of the language they are learning in today's globalized society, fostering students' cultural competency might serve as another key concern in language instruction. It is widely known that coping with students from diverse cultural origins and language proficiency presents a big difficulty. This requires a more inclusive approach of language teaching instructions that might value linguistic diversity.

Last but not least, one more key issue in language teaching of the 21st century is assessment. Standardized tests and written exams are examples of traditional assessment approaches that might not be able to measure students' communication or language ability effectively. To get a more complete picture of their students' language proficiency, teachers should

investigate alternate assessment techniques such as projects, portfolios, and performance-based evaluations.

Differentiated instruction as an alternative solution.

A useful strategy that can assist in addressing a number of the problems that face language training in the twenty-first century is differentiated instruction. A more inclusive and productive learning environment can be created by educators by customizing education to match the various requirements of pupils. Differentiated instruction can address the following problems in language instruction:

1. With differentiated education, educators can modify their use of technology according to students' access and comfort level with digital resources. To ensure that all learners have equitable access to language learning tools, teachers can offer substitute activities for those who do not have access to technology at home.

2. Teachers can enhance their classes by incorporating a variety of cultural viewpoints and experiences through differentiated instruction. It is possible to establish a more inclusive classroom that fosters cultural competency in all students by acknowledging and appreciating the cultural backgrounds of the students. Also by offering individualized support and resources, differentiated teaching enables teachers to serve students who speak multiple languages. To fulfill the special requirements of multilingual students, educators can provide resources that are tailored to the language, chances for peer cooperation, and differentiated evaluations.

3. Differentiated instruction promotes the use of a range of evaluation techniques that take into account each student's unique learning preferences and skills. Teachers can measure students' learning more precisely when they provide alternative assessment options, like multimedia projects, oral presentations, or performance-based assignments.

Conclusion

It is known that the twenty-first century is intricate and multidimensional, requiring teachers to handle a variety of difficulties and problems in the task of teaching languages. Addressing topics like technological integration, cultural competency, multilingualism, and assessment is very important for language teachers, since it might effect on preparation of the learners for success in an increasingly interconnected world. Educators can apply differentiated instruction that might assist in meeting the many demands of 21st-century learners and by this way foster meaningful language learning experiences. Applying differentiated instruction ideas into practice, teachers not only may make language learning more accessible and interesting but also equipping students with the skills they need to thrive in a world which is becoming more interconnected day by day.

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